

Data Organization

Organize your data with a clear folder structure and consistent file names. This allows you and others to easily locate, access and use your data, to avoid duplication, and to ensure that your data can be backed up.

Use suitable file formats

Careful selection of [file formats](#) is crucial for ensuring that your files remain accessible, interoperable, properly archivable, and can still be used after many years. Aspects of a suitable file format are:

- No restrictive licenses
- Readable by many software products (at best by open source/code software)
- No encryption or digital rights management (DRM) – in case sharing is allowed
- Established in the research community
- Openly accessible documentation

Use a file naming convention

Use consistent, meaningful file names. Include the following elements:

- Project/event or research team/department (abbreviation)
- Author (whole name or initials)
- Keyword(s) describing the content of the file
- Date ([YYYY-MM-DD](#)) and/or version

Not all characters are allowed for folder and file naming! Do not use spaces and/or special characters in the file name. Max. absolute path length: 255 characters.

Use a folder structure

- Organize your data logically in a hierarchical [folder structure](#).
- Separate active and completed work and delete any temporary files after use.
- Don't make the folder structure too nested, this can lead to long and complicated file paths.

Add documentation and metadata

Good [documentation](#) (e.g. in a readme file) facilitates the reuse of data – both for others and for yourself. An important element of documentation is metadata. [Metadata](#) are structured and machine-readable information about a (data) object. Metadata are therefore data about data. Metadata include, for example, information on title, creator, date, license, file format and persistent identifier. If there is no domain-specific or institutional standard for documentation, it is recommended to define an internal project standard.

'How-to' tips for data organization:

1. Do as much of the data organization as possible during the project. Cleaning up after a person has already left is usually difficult.
2. Have regular data cleaning days in your research group (similar to lab cleaning days), for example every 3 months or once per semester.
3. Let other group members look at your data organization to help you improve e.g. your folder structure, file naming, or data documentation.
4. Optimally, group leaders (PIs) enforce data clean up and set data organization/deletion deadlines.

